

Constructing Old Age in Communist Bulgaria: Ideology, Policy, Science

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Abstract: The article explores the production of knowledge and images of old age in communist Bulgaria, comparing three types of hegemonic discourses, offering different conceptualizations of ageing and the elderly: the ideological, the political, and the scientific. The source for the ideological discourse is the official newspaper *Rabotnichesko Delo*, insofar as it offers representations of old people and their roles in society. The state policies towards older people are discussed based primarily on pension laws. For the scientific discourse, gerontological literature from the 1960s–1970s is reviewed. The study reveals the dynamics, the tensions and the contradictions within and between the three types of discourse.

Keywords: ageing, Bulgaria, gerontology, old people, pension laws

Age is a basic social-science category, together with gender, race, class and ethnicity. Age defines, on the one hand, some of the important social roles of the individuals and, on the other hand, some of the social groupings in which they can participate. Unlike gender and race, which are mostly perceived as given and immutable, age is more elusive as individuals enter and exit different age-related roles and groupings over the course of their lives. Age characteristics are relevant in relation to life course (to indicate whether someone is young, middle-aged or old), and in relation to generation (to differentiate between cohorts). Social change induces changes in the scenarios of ageing and in the meanings and representations of age/ing. As sociologist of ageing Matilda Riley argued, ‘the meanings we attach to age have power. They become stereotypes, shaping our personal plans, hopes, and fears. They become age constraints, built into the social structure, molding the course of our lives...’¹

In this article, I am interested in the changes of the meanings and the representations of age in communist Bulgaria (1944-1989). The self-understanding of the regime at a semantic level was initially associated with youth as a generalising metaphor of the ‘new order’. This rhetoric had its correlatives at the policy level, with the regime undermining traditional intergenerational relations and co-opting young people. While the policies towards youth and their effects have been amply explored,² research interest in ageing and

¹ M.W. Riley, ‘Aging, social change, and the power of ideas’, *Daedalus*, 107, 4 (1978), 39–52, 49.

² Among the various aspects investigated are childhood (e.g. D. Koleva [ed.], *Detstvo pri socializma: politicheski, institutsionalni i biografichni perspektivi* [Sofia 2010]), youth brigades (e.g. B. Raeva, *Migratsiata selo–grad po vreme na socializma (po primera na Dimitrovgrad)* [Dimitrovgrad 2017]), leisure and popular

old people in communist Bulgaria has awakened only recently.³ My aim is to contribute to this strand of research on the socialist life course by enquiring into the ideological, political and scientific discourses about old age and old people. I focus on these three hegemonic discourses as technologies of demarcation and construction of old age and of old people as a social category. Their mirroring and/or subversions from below – an important issue in itself – will be left out of this article, as will be other realms of imagining old age, such as popular media, literature and art.

I adopt a broadly constructivist perspective informed by Katz and asking about the political, social and epistemological conditions of the production of knowledge about old age.⁴ How were the specific subjects of such knowledge constructed? What about its regimes of legitimation and authorization? What social technologies were employed for its production? Which deeper political, social and institutional realities were hidden under the rhetorical surfaces? The study is partly situated in the tradition of the reflexive history of gerontology set by Achenbaum and Green.⁵ More specifically, it adds to the emerging body of research on gerontology in the Soviet-bloc countries.⁶ However, this is not a history of Bulgarian gerontology. Building on Koleva and Petrov's pioneering study, I broaden the perspective to capture the 'politics of knowledge' (Sivaramakrishnan) about old age and old people crafted within three distinct hegemonic discourses. Thereby, my project contributes to the burgeoning field of ageing studies, where Eastern Europe has only recently been mapped.⁷

Before moving on to the discourses, I shall briefly introduce their historical and social context. The demographic dynamics in 20th-century Bulgaria followed the general trends: decreasing child mortality, declining birth rates, rising life expectancy. As a result, the share of people aged over 60 steadily increased: from 9.8 % in 1900, to 11.6 % in 1946,

culture (e.g. K. Taylor, *Let's twist again: Youth and leisure in socialist Bulgaria* [Münster 2004]), forms of resistance and disciplining (e.g. A. Angelov, 'Zozas, swings, hooligans, and other personages of "inappropriate" behaviour in caricatures – Bulgaria 1940s–1960s', in D. Demski, A. Kassabova, I.Sz. Kristof, L. Laineste, K. Baraniecka-Olszewska [eds] *The Multi-Mediatized Other: The construction of Reality in East-Central Europe, 1945–1980* [Budapest 2017], 424–39), opposition to the regime (e.g. P. Angelova, 'Mladezhkata politicheska saprotiva (1944–1949)', unpublished PhD thesis, Sofia University 2024).

³ D. Koleva (ed.) *Vazrastta pri socializma: pokolenia v semeistvoto i obshtestvoto* (Sofia 2019); I. Eftimova, *Etnolozhki aspekti na starostta i ostaryavaneto v bulgarskoto obshtestvo* (Shumen 2022); *Bulgarska Etnologia*. Thematic issue 'Etnologia na starostta', XLVI, 1 (2020), ed. by I. Iliev.

⁴ S. Katz, *Disciplining Old Age: The Formation of Gerontological Knowledge* (Charlottesville & London 1996), 7.

⁵ W. A. Achenbaum, *Crossing Frontiers: Gerontology emerges as a science* (Cambridge 1995); B. S. Green, *Gerontology and the Construction of Old Age* (London and New York 2017 [1st ed. 1993]) for gerontology in USA, M. Bernard, M. Ray and J. Reynolds, *The Evolution of British Gerontology: Personal perspectives and historical developments* (Bristol 2020) for UK; H. W. Park, *Old Age, New Science: Gerontologists and Their Biosocial Visions, 1900-1960* (Pittsburgh 2016) for both USA and UK.

⁶ S. Grant and I. McK. Scarborough (eds), *Geriatrics and Ageing in the Soviet Union: Medical, Political and Social Contexts* (London, New York 2023); D. Koleva and I. Petrov, 'Socialist gerontology? Or gerontology during socialism? The Bulgarian case', *History of the Human Sciences*, 36, 3–4 (2023), 178–201 for communist Bulgaria. See also I. McK. Scarborough, 'A New Science for an Old(er) Population: Soviet Gerontology and Geriatrics in International Comparative Perspective', *Social History of Medicine*, 35, 4 (2022), 1247–66 for telling parallels in the establishment of gerontology as a research field in USA and the Soviet Union.

⁷ D. Gramshammer-Hohl and O. Hergenröther (eds), *Foreign Countries of Old Age: East and Southeast European Perspectives on Aging* (Aging Studies Volume XIX) (Bielefeld 2021). See also Grant and Scarborough, *Geriatrics and Ageing in the Soviet Union* for the Soviet Union and communist Poland.

13 % in 1956, 16.1 % in 1965, 18.4 % in 1975 and 21.1 % in 1985.⁸ The kolkhoz-type collectivization of the agricultural land proved to be a strong push factor for rural youth to migrate to urban settlements, especially to industrial sites. This is why, by late 1970s, the share of the elderly in rural areas was twice higher than that in towns.⁹ The living conditions of the rural elderly were significantly worse than those of the urbanites: for example, 77 % of them had no running water in their houses.¹⁰ The pensions were generally low, with about two-thirds of them below the minimum wage.¹¹ This was a plausible reason for the relatively high participation of pensioners in wage labour: on average, 18.4 % of all retirees were employed. For the first five years after retirement age, the share of working pensioners was 40.7 % of the men and 32.8 % of the women.¹² Nevertheless, c. 20 % of the retirees received financial help from their adult children, most often in cases of unplanned expenses. The intergenerational transactions flew in the other direction as well, predominantly in kind: 52 % of the elderly (mostly rural residents) engaged in gardening and 47 % in animal husbandry, providing for their children and grandchildren.¹³ These data, collected in the late 1970s, give a fair idea of the trends in the situation of the retirees and the intergenerational transactions that started in the preceding couple of decades, with the rapid industrialization and rural-urban migration.

The response of the regime to alarming demographic trends was strongly pro-natalist,¹⁴ an orientation that no doubt influenced the cultural coding of old age in communist Bulgaria. In what follows, I shall focus on the production of knowledge and representations of ageing and the elderly through the ideology, social policy, and science. The aim is to reveal the dynamics, the tensions and the contradictions within and between them, how they fed into each other and what they reveal about public attitudes and state policies toward the elderly. I tap into the ideological discourse by reviewing those publications in the official newspaper *Rabotnichesko Delo*, which represented old people and their roles in the socialist society. To understand the state policies towards older people, I draw primarily on pension laws, supplementing them with statistical analysis and highlighting the gender dimension. Finally, the scientific discourse is developed in the gerontological literature published from the 1960s on, when gerontology was institutionalized in Bulgaria. In addition to specialized and popular texts, I draw on the archive of the key institution where gerontology research was developed in the 1970s and 1980s.

These are three very different types of sources with different underlying conceptualizations of age, to which I apply an interpretive methodology of close reading to reveal the vocabularies and rhetorics whereby knowledge of ageing and old age was

⁸ T. Arnaudova, M. Foteva, V. Pavlova, *Prouchvane na usloviata na zivot i sotsialnite problemi na naselenieto v nadtrudosposobna vyzrast v Bulgaria* (Sofia 1984), 12; T. Arnaudova, 'Sotsialni problemi na naselenieto ot tretata vazrast', in Central Statistical Office: *Analytical Reports 2* (Sofia 1988), 192-209, 192.

⁹ Arnaudova, Foteva, Pavlova, *Prouchvane na usloviata*, 13-14.

¹⁰ Arnaudova, *Sotsialni problemi*, 201-2.

¹¹ *Ibid.*, 199. More details on the pension policies follow in section 2.

¹² *Ibid.*, 203.

¹³ *Ibid.*, 206.

¹⁴ A. Kassabova, 'Reproduktivnata politika v NRB – mezhduradnata i otrichane na realnostta', in E. Troeva (ed.) *Kulturna i meditsinska antropologia* (Sofia 2015).

produced and circulated, as well as the underlying interests, which informed respective attitudes and policies. I start with the production of discursive stereotypes, which were most widely spread through *Rabotnichesko Delo* as an authoritative media channel, and then zoom in on the expert discourses of law and science.

1. Ideological discourses: from ‘senile reactionaries’ to custodians of traditions

In order to capture the ideological aspects of the construction of old age, I shall start ‘at the surface of textual events’¹⁵ limiting myself to discourse analysis of publications in *Rabotnichesko Delo*, the official newspaper of the regime. This newspaper was chosen as the utmost mouthpiece of the ‘authoritarian discourse’ (Bakhtin), pronouncing on all current issues every day of the regime’s existence. It was the most widely spread one, as libraries and organisations subscribed to it on a mandatory basis. Thus it had a substantial influence on the public opinion and on the broader societal perceptions on various themes, including old age. The questions with which I approach it ask about the rhetoric of presentation of older people: how they were portrayed, what qualities of theirs were emphasised, which roles they were cast into. For the purpose of this study, I sampled 15 annual runs for the period 1950 to 1989, focusing on the early 1950s, as well as the years when Family Codes were adopted: 1968 and 1985.¹⁶ The focus on the first half of the 1950s is driven by the consideration that during this period, in contrast to later years, the propaganda discourse was not yet (fully) standardized and ritualized: it still largely referred to specific contexts and was in this sense ‘literal’.

Ageing and the aged *qua* aged were not among the preferred topics of the party newspaper: they appear occasionally in texts featuring intergenerational ruptures and continuities. Normally, such texts appeared once or twice a month, unless there was some special occasion, such as an anniversary. Their focus was more often on the young rather than the elderly, and their authors were journalists, with very few exceptions, such as comments on the reforms in the Pension Act, which I shall discuss in the next section.

The close reading of the texts in which old people were presented yielded three distinct types of representations: negative – the old opposing the young, positive – the old acting as young, and patronising – the old in the care of the young.

In the 1950s, the newspaper *Rabotnichesko Delo* abounded with headlines about young shock workers, young mechanics, weavers and builders. The young representatives of the then-new vocations, such as tractor drivers and crane operators, were presented as bearers of the new, who defied their parents in a way that would have been unthinkable before. By contrast, the parents, i.e. the ‘old’ ones, were stereotyped as conservative, traditionalist, unable to grasp the novelties. Young Nedelcho Vatskov, foreman of the tractor brigade, was presented through the conflict with his father. The ‘old man’ Vatskov did not accept the innovation of filling up the seeders on the move and scolded his son:

¹⁵ Green, *Gerontology and the Construction of Old Age*, 39.

¹⁶ For a more detailed account see D. Koleva, ‘Ot “dartata reaktsia” do “aktivnite bortsii”: ideologicheski konstrukti i socialni scenarii na starostta’, in M. Gruev (ed.) *Prepodrezhdaneto na obshtestvoto. Stranitsi ot sotsialnata istoria na komunizma v Bulgaria* (Sofia 2021), 123–58.

“You may be in a hurry to get an award, but we won’t let you waste the seed!” the old man frowns, “take me to see how you fill them.” With a condescending smile on his lips, the son thinks, “What a supervisor!” and the father, though he has convinced himself that the seed is not being wasted, is unwilling to admit defeat: “Chief! Where did such a one come from, to kick against his father?” the old man fumed.¹⁷

The dramatization of the conflict rests on the traditional roles of the generations in the family: the elders give orders and the young obey. The obvious implication was that these roles were changing and the time of the old people had passed.

The intergenerational opposition was even more spectacular when a daughter, like young Elena, opposed her ‘old man’.¹⁸ She left her parents’ home secretly to enrol in a tractor-driver school because ‘staying at home, learning to weave on a wooden loom is so boring and pointless now, when there is such a new life everywhere’. When she comes back clad in the uniform of a tractor-driver and with a Stalin-style cap on her head, the father ‘keeps his hands in his belt, he doesn’t want to shake hands with the unruly daughter’. But a smile lingers under his moustache: he has reconciled. The traditional belt and the Stalin-style cap metonymically represent the two generations and more generally – the ‘old’ and the ‘new’. The fathers – i.e. old people as embodiment of past ways and values – are effectively disempowered. The regime has tangibly interfered with the intergenerational relations in the families.

Ten years later, with industrialization well under way, there is no longer conflict between generations. The fathers have retreated, excluded from the common collective goal. Fathers and sons now represent societal generations, which inhabit different worlds:

The fathers said nothing. They didn’t raise a hand to stop their children. Bulgaria is building Kremikovtzi [metallurgical plant near Sofia]. Bulgaria wanted them – them, the children, and they became builders. The fathers were proud. The fathers – the ploughmen of old, for whom the world fit into the space enclosed by the horizon line of the hills around their villages. This was their world. ...

The fathers did not know...¹⁹

Undermining traditional gender- and age-specific roles, such newspaper stories portrayed older people negatively, as relics of the ‘old world’: misunderstanding, sometimes hostile; unneeded, sometimes even harmful as carriers of obsolete values and practices; evoking condescension, if not disapproval. Thus, by associating older generations with conservatism, retrogression, and allegiance to the previous regime, and youth/young people with progress and the new order, the authoritarian discourse naturalized the revolution, presenting it as inevitable generational change.

However, there is another, entirely positive line of representation of age that links the latter to the history of the communist movement. While old parents frown, fawn, obstruct, misunderstand and finally retreat defeated, old communists are a completely different kind of people: they encourage, train, educate, guide and pass on their experience to the young. Tractor-driver Stoyanka, for example, became a shock worker for a reason: she was the

¹⁷ *Rabotnichesko delo* (hereafter RD), No. 51 / 20.02.1952.

¹⁸ RD, No. 11 / 11.01.1951.

¹⁹ RD, No. 115 / 25.04.1963.

daughter of an old communist who had emigrated to the Soviet Union and brought back precious Soviet experience.²⁰ Such cases suggest a thorough harmony and understanding between generations, a theme that became dominant in the following decades. Old age proved valuable when ideologically correct. This is evident in the quasi-patriarchal rhetoric on the anniversaries of communist-party leaders. They were not just ‘old’ but ‘old [i.e. long-term] communists’, veterans. Their life experiences, implied by age, were valuable due to their contribution to the communist party and its struggles. This was the highlight about 124-year-old Stoyan Rukov.²¹ Stoyan welcomed the Russian troops in 1878, and in 1941-44 he helped the partisans. At the age of 109, he joined the village collective. That is, it was not his exceptional age per se that was noteworthy, but his service to the regime.

Another positive representation of advanced age suggested that it was not a barrier to continued work. The featured cases followed the same model: ‘The Old Teacher’ who ‘continues to do her highly noble duty’,²² ‘The Old Miner’,²³ who worked 43 years underground, the ‘Old Master-builder’ whose work ‘brought joy to people’,²⁴ the ‘Old Collective Farmer’ who over-delivered on the milk plan.²⁵ The construction worker Ivan Kantardzhiev, aged 67, when asked why he was still working, he would think:

*Can you separate work from life? From the life for which you have walked the ranks of the strikers, experienced the strength of the police batons? Taking the pensioner’s rosary is easier, but when you don’t have to, it’s humiliating. No, he prefers the trowel instead.*²⁶

The idea that retirement was humiliating, if not prescribed for health reasons, was not a mere compensatory rhetoric to discursively counter the actual marginalisation of the elderly. It corresponded with the legal regulations about pensioners’ employment, which will be discussed below. The coordination of normative measures and propaganda efforts speaks of the gravity of the labour shortages in certain regions and certain sectors of the economy.

A new theme that emerged in the 1980s was intergenerational continuity in the context of tradition, and hence valuing old people as bearers of ‘folk’ traditions. The reporter from a village holiday admired ‘the vitality of the old women wearing their traditional attire.’²⁷ The elders now ‘sat on their roots’, preserved traditions and passed them on to the young. This turn towards a positive association of old age with national tradition was likely linked with the increasingly explicit nationalist orientation of the regime.

The third type of representations appeared in the 1960s and developed in the following decades, as the moralising on the topic of intergenerational relations in the family gained ground. The position was now reversed: instead of declaring itself an ally of the young in the eternal intergenerational tensions, *Rabotnichesko Delo* reproached them for a lack of care and attention to their elderly parents. The case of 106-year-old Stoyana, mother of eight but left alone in her old age, stirred bitter indignation:

²⁰ RD, No. 67 / 8.03.1950.

²¹ RD, No. 222 / 10.08.1959.

²² RD, No. 215 / 2.08.1956.

²³ RD, No. 304 / 30.10.1956.

²⁴ RD, No. 1 / 1.01.1967.

²⁵ RD, No. 39 / 8.02.1967.

²⁶ RD, No. 86 / 26.03.1964.

²⁷ RD, No. 21 / 21.01.1984.

*The 'son' is ashamed of his mother, of her old clothes, he is afraid of the expenses around her! Is there a more sordid feeling on earth than this?! – the author asked indignantly, and reminded: When the son's conscience is asleep, there is a power that must awaken it. That is the power of public opinion.*²⁸

Following the wide response to this publication, the newspaper devoted an editorial to the issue of filial duty.²⁹ It noted 'the lack of filial affection in some citizens, for whom old parents are almost a burden. But these are manifestations profoundly alien to our socialist reality'. The care of old parents – both as filial affection and as material support – was presented as the first and irrevocable duty of their adult children, required by communist morality. This norm was explicitly codified in 1985, with the adoption of the new Family Code.³⁰ By that time, the demographic structure had significantly changed: the share of the urban population had risen from 25 % to 65 % due to massive rural-urban migration in the preceding two decades; the share of two-generation households had increased, as well as that of one- and two-member households of retirees. The latter comprised 15 % and 37 % respectively (that is, more than half) of the population aged 60 and above.³¹ The moral arbitrage of intergenerational relations, which in the first decade of the regime was invariably and vigorously on the side of the young, had now switched to a different register of values.³² The Family Code revived the idea of the three-generation family, which had to cater for both socialization of the children and care for the elderly.

The three directions of the authoritative discourse outlined here developed in a loose chronological sequence. First, in the 1950s, came the theme of intergenerational conflict where the regime sided with the young, disempowering the elderly and seriously undermining traditional family relations. This happened not only at the discursive level, but also at the social level, as a result of migration, higher educational levels, the introduction of new professions and new practices of living and socialising, as well as economically: through the dispossession of agricultural land and urban properties. During the same period, the ideologization of age emerged: old people were generally presented as conservative, ignorant and retrograde, but old communists were totally different. They had a presence and a voice: they gave interviews, their stories were told, their agency was confirmed. Still, it was less about personalities than about models to be followed by others. This tendency developed in the following decades, when the celebration of intergenerational continuity and the association of old age with national traditions displaced the theme of conflict. The on-going changes in the structure of the households and the pattern of family life gave rise to

²⁸ RD, No. 39 / 8.02.1963.

²⁹ RD, No. 84 / 25.03.1963.

³⁰ While the economic obligations of parents to children were comprehensively codified, children's responsibility for their elderly parents was obliterated in the family law of 1949 and later re-installed but only as moral duty. S. Balutzova, 'Otnoshenia "roditeli-detsa" spored bulgarskoto sotsialisticheskoto zakonodatelstvo (po primeri ot Zakona za litsata i semeistvoto i semeinite kodeksi ot 1968 i 1985 g.)', in D. Koleva (ed.) *Vazrastta pri sotsializma*, 75-93.

³¹ Arnaudova, *Sotsialni problemi*, 193.

³² An additional circumstance could have been the gradual morphing of the communist party-state into a 'gerontocracy': while in 1954 the average age of the Politburo of the Bulgarian communist party was 49.7 years, in 1989 it was already 65.5 years. K. Metodiev, *Pokolenia i vazrast v politikata. Bulgarskiat prehod* (Sofia 2012), 72-3.

new problems to which the third direction of thematization of old age corresponds: as needing and receiving (or not) care from the younger generations in the family. While the efforts of the state in providing for the old age of the working people were highlighted, the elderly found themselves left mostly, if not entirely, to the care of their adult children. Behind the moralising rhetoric there was an unstated but consistent withdrawal from the revolutionary generational rebellion towards traditional models of family and household, enshrined in the Family Code of 1985.³³ Thereby, the state assumed a patronising stance towards the elderly insisting that they be taken care of by their families and keeping for itself a controlling role.

2. Policies: from ‘well-deserved rest’ to labour reserve

In this section, I move from the ideological level to that of institutions or, figuratively speaking, from metaphors to categories. As Mary Douglas has shown, institutions think in categories that they themselves have invented.³⁴ Their optics and their toolkits are applicable to social groups delimited according to set criteria. The main criterion of such delimitation, according to which the modern state constructs the standard life path of its citizens, is age. Age determines entry into and exit from the education system and the labour market. From this point of view, social old age is normatively determined by the age of retirement. Already in 1924, the Social Security Act defined old age as ‘reaching a certain age, regardless of the amount of work capacity of the insured individual’.³⁵ Under the communist regime, where private livelihoods and liberal professions were eliminated or reduced to a minimum, the end of the working life at retirement age became even more important. In this section, I will examine old age through the institutional gaze, primarily the pension legislation and its implementation. While there were other forms of state care for old people, such as nursing homes and, in later years, home assistance (‘patronage’), pensions were the only regular, guaranteed and universal form of state care for the elderly.

The social old age set by the 1924 law was 60 years. The pension legislation during the communist period did not diverge significantly from this standard. It set retirement age at 55 for women and 60 for men. Importantly, the Pension Act of 1957 set requirements for the duration of service depending on gender and the type/category of work.³⁶ Individuals who met those requirements were treated in the law as pensioners, regardless of whether they continued working or not. The age and required length of service varied depending on the category of labour, defined by subordinate legislation. The first category included work in hard and harmful conditions (e.g. underground). Initially, police and army officers fell into this category as well.

Work category	Women-age	Women-service	Men-age	Men-service
I	45	15	50	15
II	50	20	55	20

³³ DV, No. 138 / 18.05.1985.

³⁴ M. Douglas, *How Institutions Think* (Syracuse NY 1986).

³⁵ Art. 3, Darzhaven vestnik [State Gazette] (hereafter DV), No. 289 / 25.03.1924.

³⁶ DV, No. 91 / 12.11.1957.

III	55	20	60	25
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Table 1. Criteria for retiring: age and duration of service, according to the Pension Act of 1957.

The Law on the Retirement of the Members of Agricultural Collectives (1957) envisaged similar requirements. A telling regulation was Article 5, whereby pensioners were entitled to their full pension if they continued to work on the collective farms.³⁷ Possible reason for this were the very low pensions provided by the collectives (several times lower than those defined by the Pension Act for state employees). Another reason could be that agricultural labour was already much less attractive than its alternatives. Later amendments serve to prove this: retired members of the collectives were entitled to their full pension only if they did not occupy administrative, engineering or mechanic's positions after retirement.³⁸

At the time of the adoption of these laws, part of the workforce in the country was 'idle' (the term 'unemployed' was no longer in use: theoretically, unemployment could not exist in a socialist society).³⁹ Therefore the option of early retirement existed: at 55 for men and at 50 for women. Pensioners who were employed could not receive a pension in addition to the salary – a rule that could dis-incentivize working retirees. In later years however, the regulations defining the criteria for retirement, including the categories of labour (in force as of 1 January 1961), were judged to be too liberal: in 1961 alone, the number of 1st-category pensions almost tripled from 2135 to 5964.⁴⁰ At that time already, labour shortages were beginning to be felt in some branches of the economy. This is why the Pension Act was amended to allow the Council of Ministers to decide on the conditions under which working pensioners could receive a part of their pension on top of the salary.⁴¹

These regulations exhibit certain tensions between the efforts to maintain social welfare and to control social expenses. They also mark a tendency that developed in subsequent years until the end of the regime. For that period, over 30 amendments to the Pension Act were adopted, and over 40 amendments to the Regulations for its implementation, in addition to over 20 specific decrees and ordinances. The sheer numbers speak not only about the importance of the issue, but also about the complexity and the changing nature of the tasks that retirement policies sought to resolve. The policies seem to have been designed in a piecemeal way, in response to immediate challenges. Most of the amendments were along three main lines. First, as in theory inflation could not exist in a socialist economy, the indexation of the pensions to compensate for the actual inflation was each time effectuated through a special decision: an amendment of the law or an ordinance of the Council of Ministers, announced to be motivated by the 'ever growing care of the Party for the elderly'. The second line of the changes provided the growing privileges of a special category of elderly people, the 'active fighters against fascism and capitalism', i.e. participants in the communist-led resistance during the Second World War.⁴² Finally, the third and most important line, which is of particular interest here, regulated the conditions

³⁷ DV, No. 1 / 1.01.1957.

³⁸ RD, No. 35 / 4.02.1967.

³⁹ A. Minchev, 'Pensionnoto delo – v saotvetstvie sas savremenntie uslovia', RD, No. 1 / 1.01.1968.

⁴⁰ Ibid.

⁴¹ DV, No. 51 / 27.06.1961.

⁴² For details see D. Koleva, 'How can care produce inequality? The privileges of the "active fighters against fascism and capitalism" in communist Bulgaria', *Südost Forschungen* 82, 2023, 26-46.

under which pensioners were allowed to work. It reveals both the construction of the legal old age and the actual policies in relation to the elderly.

By 1966, the total number of the pensions was already 1.6 million, the population of Bulgaria being 8.2 million. The early retirement of working-age people was proven to be economically and socially unjustified. Therefore, significant changes in the provisions concerning retirement were introduced with the Decree of the Central Committee of the Communist Party and the Council of Ministers of 28 December 1967.⁴³ Early retirement was cancelled, the work in the police and the army, as well as some industries, was re-categorized from the first to the second category, which implied longer service and later retirement. These measures were justified with the improved living and working conditions, and the improved health care, which presumably led to increased average longevity and retention of work capacity. At the same time, incentives were created for industrial and agricultural workers to postpone their retirement: they were entitled to a 3 % increase of their future pension for each year of work after reaching retirement age. More importantly, it was already possible to receive both salary and pension, if retirees were employed as 'immediate' (i.e. blue-collar) workers in agriculture, mining, lumbering, or construction.⁴⁴ Two years later, this opportunity was extended to retirees who worked in the canning industry – thus signalling another branch of the economy in need for hands.⁴⁵ In 1970, another expansion followed, including the maintenance of highways and the repair of railway and automobile equipment; geological exploration works; fisheries; postal services; public catering; the operating of heating installations; work as orderlies in health and social institutions; as porters and night guards.⁴⁶

In subsequent years, the regulations of pensioners' employment were refined and detailed according to the category of the retirees: military, 'active fighters', managerial and 'highly-paid' personnel, etc., as well as the type of the work contract (full-time or part-time), and the amount of the salary.⁴⁷ In an apparent effort after social justice, workers with low salaries and part-time workers were entitled to receive their full pension, while higher-paid working retirees could get only a limited part, or none of it. This principle did not apply to the chronically understaffed branches of the economy: those who worked in agriculture, mining, and construction were entitled to their full pensions. Ordinance No. 18 of the Council of Ministers of April 1985 enumerated over 20 industries where pensioners employed as 'immediate workers' could receive both salary and pension, among them metallurgy and machine construction; oil, chemical and rubber industry; textile and sewing industry; leather, fur and shoe industries, etc.⁴⁸ Moreover, this entitlement was extended to all low-paid service and executive staff and to retirees employed in educational, cultural and

⁴³ DV, No. 102 / 29.12.1967. Legal provisions for paid work beyond retirement were already present in the Soviet Union (G. Stoynev, 'Medico-sotsialni problemi v gerontologiat i geriatriata', *Problemi na gerontologiat i geriatriata*, 1 (1965), 90-107, 103-4). They might have served as a model for the Decree in question.

⁴⁴ Ibid.

⁴⁵ DV, No. 59 / 29.07.1969.

⁴⁶ DV, No. 63 / 11.08.1970.

⁴⁷ DV, No. 53 / 11.07.1975.

⁴⁸ DV, No. 32 / 23.04.1985 г.

health institutions with salaries below 170 lv/month.⁴⁹ The managers and the trade unions were tasked to dissuade the workers from retiring and encourage them to opt for later retirement, unless there were younger candidates for the respective position.

These regulations leave the impression of panic vis-à-vis severe shortages of workers. They confirm the conditionality of the legal construction of advanced (non-working) age and reveal that the regime was indeed interested in the elderly but not in terms of providing care for them, as suggested by the late ideological discourse. The actual interest was in using pensioners as labour force, primarily in unattractive, low-qualified jobs. For this, the term ‘residual work capacity’ was introduced, and the task to utilize it.

From the legal perspective, pensioners appear mostly genderless. In reality, gender was quite important. The relatively young age of retirement was a prerequisite for the organization of housework, with retired women undertaking a significant part of it, such as work in the homestead (in rural areas), doing the cooking and the shopping, standing in lines, etc. Retired grandparents – more often women than men – took care of their grandchildren, from taking them to walks and helping with the lessons, to accepting them to live in their home and providing for them for long periods. These practices have led anthropologist Katherine Verdery to conclude that ‘social reproduction was geriatrized’ – an observation made about Romania but equally true about Bulgaria as well.⁵⁰ This is why, it can be expected that the post-retirement roles of men and women would be different, and the legal provisions discussed above would mostly refer to men.

A comprehensive study commissioned by the government in 1979, paid special attention to the economic activities of retirees in Bulgaria. The comparison of the share of ‘economically active’ (i.e. working) pensioners in 1965 and 1975 revealed a dramatic fall: from 24 % of the pensioners (318 thousand) to 12.3 % (198 thousand: 18.1 % of the men and 8.3 % of the women). The differences were the greatest for the 70+ year-olds: those among them who still worked in 1975 were three times fewer than in 1965 (women – 4.4 times, men – 2.6 times), while the working pensioners aged 60-69 years were twice as fewer in 1975 compared to 1965. The authors estimated this tendency as a positive one: in their interpretation, retired people were better off in 1975 and had no need for additional income.⁵¹ Another factor explaining the decrease of the pensioners’ work outside the home was ‘the concentration, modernization and the implementation of highly productive machinery in agriculture, the industrialization, the growing requirements to the productivity and effectiveness of labour, which hampers the participation of older people together with the young’.⁵² In line with this observation, 170 thousand (85.8 %) of the economically active pensioners worked in the ‘material production’ (an euphemism for low-qualified jobs), mostly in agriculture (101 thousand), industry, construction and services. The rest (28 thousand) remained active primarily in education and health care.⁵³ Pensioners filled in positions in those branches of the economy where labour shortage was chronic: they made up

⁴⁹ The average monthly wage for 1985 was 213 lv: <https://nssi.bg/wp-content/uploads/SMRZ.pdf> accessed 15 February 2025.

⁵⁰ K. Verdery, *What was socialism and what comes next* (Princeton 1996), 65.

⁵¹ Arnaudova, Foteva, Pavlova, *Prouchvane na usloviata*, 22.

⁵² *Ibid.*

⁵³ *Ibid.*, 62.

20.5 % of all employees in animal husbandry and 10.1 % of those employed in crop production. The great majority of them had manual jobs: 36.6 % of those who had white-collar jobs before retirement, took manual jobs afterwards.⁵⁴ This was a stable tendency, confirmed by the Decree of the Council of Ministers and the Central Council of the Trade Unions of September 1985, which ordered all ministries, companies, organizations and local authorities ‘to create the necessary conditions for attracting to work, primarily in the material production and services, workers on supplementary and second employment contracts, and for the broad inclusion of pensioners in these activities.’⁵⁵

At the same time, according to the Family Code (1985), care for the elderly lay primarily on their families and adult children. This was already evident in the 1979 survey, which revealed that only 4.1 % of the respondents had received social aid, while intergenerational help within the families was the rule: almost 60 % of the elderly reported that they helped their children and 43.6 % – that they received help from them.⁵⁶ Moreover, the Family Code assigned caring roles to grandparents, especially grandmothers: they were entitled to maternity leave instead of the mothers, if they took care of their young grandchildren. As anthropologist Ilia Iliev has concluded, this was ‘a brutal and efficient solution of the problem of the double burden (work and domestic chores plus childcare) for women in socialism [...], the domestic work was delegated to retired women’.⁵⁷ Thus, while the policies – or at least, the rhetoric – towards the young proclaimed gender equality, the elderly were pushed into the traditional roles of women as housekeepers and men as breadwinners, encouraged to take manual jobs.⁵⁸

What is seen from the pension legislature and its implementation is that the elderly were interesting for the state primarily as a labour resource to be tapped in, especially in branches of the economy that were unattractive and chronically understaffed, and in low-qualified positions often requiring hard physical work in deleterious conditions. This is why the law included incentives for ‘immediate workers’, but not for administrative personnel or for work on prestigious jobs.

3. Gerontology: from active ageing to medicalization of old age

Although ageing and longevity had stirred the interest of scholars since earlier in the 20th century, gerontology was established in Bulgaria in 1963 with the founding of the Centre for Gerontology and Geriatrics (CGG) in Sofia. This section is based mainly on CGG

⁵⁴ Ibid., 64.

⁵⁵ RD, No. 263 / 20.09.1985.

⁵⁶ Arnaudova, Foteva, Pavlova, *Prouchvane na usloviata*, 55, 57.

⁵⁷ I. Iliev, ‘Gender and Representations of Successful Old Age in Rural Bulgaria’, *Ethnologia Balkanica*, 20 (2017), 86.

⁵⁸ See I. Iliev’s comprehensive research on the conceptualization of childcare as ‘work’ and eldercare as moral duty, which started in the 1970s and ran counter to the traditional intergenerational relations. I. Iliev, ‘Retirement is a Foreign Country: Work beyond Retirement and Elder Care in Socialist Bulgaria’, *Genealogy*, 6, 65. The legal and institutional provisions strongly influenced popular ideas of gendered ‘successful ageing’, which have persisted after the demise of the regime (Iliev, Gender and Representations).

publications and on the archive of its successor institution, the Research Institute of Endocrinology, Gerontology and Geriatrics (RIEGG), established in 1972.⁵⁹

The institutionalization of gerontology in Bulgaria owes a great deal to the vision and the energy of Dragomir Mateev (1902-71), professor of physiology, long-term rector of the Sports College in Sofia. Mateev studied medicine in Germany (1920-23) and Sofia (1924-27), and had a good scholarly reputation in Bulgaria and abroad. Already in the 1930s, he published in professional journals in Germany, and took part in international congresses. His international recognition, combined with his long-standing membership in the communist party, was an obvious advantage for his career under the communist regime. Most importantly, Mateev developed an original theory of ageing and the way to slow it down. Based on his research on the physiology of work and fatigue,⁶⁰ he found that inactivity/immobilization led to degeneration and atrophy, while intensive activity ('functional loading') had an anti-entropic effect: it unlocked the processes of self-recovery and renovation. Moreover, regular loading led to the so-called 'working hypertrophy', i.e. reaching a higher level of functional potential, rather than simply restoring the initial one. The cycle of loading-fatigue-recovery to a state exceeding the baseline ('exaltation phase') was at the core of sports training and physical fitness more broadly.

Mateev extrapolated these findings onto the processes of ageing and offered a theory of physical exercise as a way to fight ageing. Starting from F. Engels' definition of life as the mode of existence of protein bodies, consisting in a perpetual self-renovation through metabolic interchange with the environment, Mateev argued that this self-renovation was not automatic but dependent on functional loading. It effectively countered the negative phenomena associated with ageing. 'While the dead machine wears out from work, the living organism builds and improves itself', he concluded optimistically.⁶¹ A further extrapolation led to a broader conceptualization of functional loading to include intellectual and cultural activities (reading, listening to music, going to the theatre, etc.), and organized social activities, since any isolation from social activities had a negative impact: it 'accelerates the processes of involution and atrophy of the brain, accelerates the weakening of both nervous processes and memory, and makes old people mentally deficient'.⁶²

These ideas, while rooted in biology, were very much akin to science utopias of the early years of the communist regimes: the belief that science would conquer nature, including human nature.⁶³ Moreover, they suggested an acceptable way to include ageing into the project of the 'new society' and the 'new man': old age could at least be postponed,

⁵⁹ For a more detailed history of Bulgarian gerontology see Koleva and Petrov, 'Socialist Gerontology'.

⁶⁰ D. Mateev and H. Petrov, 'Gravitatsionniat shok u choveka sled telesna rabota', *Spisanie na BAN*, XLVI (1934) 131-70; D. Mateeff, 'Über die Muskelermüdung. Eine Arbeitshypothese auf der Grundlage der Forschungen von I.M.Setschenov, I.P.Pavlov und N.Je.Wedenski', Paper presented at Sportärzte-Tagung (Leipzig 1951). Holding Dragomir Mateev, BAS Research Archive; D. Mateeff, 'Biologische Grundlagen des Alterns aus der Sicht des Physiologen', *Zeitschrift für Altersforschung* 12 (1971), 117-26.

⁶¹ D. Mateev, 'Starost i dalgoletie', *Problemi na gerontologijata i geriatrijata* (hereafter *PGG*), 1 (1965), 5-19, 9.

⁶² *Ibid.*, 18.

⁶³ For some fascinating case studies of science utopias in the Soviet Union see Gramshammer-Hohl and Hergenröther, *Foreign Countries of Old Age* and Grant and Scarborough, *Geriatrics and Ageing in the Soviet Union*.

if not altogether cancelled. Mateev's theory was both materialist, drawing on F. Engels and I.P. Pavlov, and empirically verifiable, backed with numerous experiments of his own and of other researchers on both sides of the Iron Curtain. No less importantly, it was optimistic, drawing a rather hopeful picture of ageing, in line with the overly optimistic rhetoric of early socialism. Old age with its degeneration (or at least, premature ageing) could be offset through physical exercise, which was accessible to everybody, and it was a matter of individual choice and persistence to do it, rather than a matter of social policy or medical intervention. More realistically, this theory propagated the ideas of active ageing, not necessarily interpreted as being 'economically active', i.e. as continuing work beyond retirement age, but not excluding that scenario either. Older people were represented as (potentially) active and capable of leading a more or less dynamic life after retirement, occupying themselves with work, physical and social activities, or hobbies. It was pointed out that idleness was wrongly considered to be a privilege of retirement age, and that this period of human life had to be filled with creativeness and optimism, including through engaging pensioners in paid work.⁶⁴ Without focusing specifically on the 'residual work capacity', CGG research potentially fed into the conceptualization of the elderly as a labour reserve.

While Mateev did not explicitly recommend postponing retirement, he mobilized the CGG team to prove the beneficial anti-entropic effects of functional loading on all levels and in all respects, thus promoting his idea of active ageing understood primarily as physical activity of the elderly, whose beneficial effect was to be proven through physiological measurements. To that end, the Physiology department focused on energy metabolism, and the ramifications of physical activity as against immobilization.⁶⁵ The researchers studied the ways to counter degeneration of the cardiovascular system through functional loading.⁶⁶ The Biochemistry and the Morphology departments studied the effects of hypodynamia on ageing organisms.⁶⁷ The Psychology department focused on mental health and the chances to improve it through physical and intellectual activities.⁶⁸ The Physical Activity department explored the effects of physical exercises to prove their importance for offsetting premature

⁶⁴ G. Stoynev, 'Mediko-socialni problemi v gerontologiatia i geriatriata', *PGG*, 1 (1965), 90–107, 103–4.

⁶⁵ L. Valnarov, 'Kam vaprosa za sastoyanieto i promentie na sadovia tonus u vazrastni i stari hora s razlichna dvigatelna aktivnost', *PGG*, 3 (1967), 195–206; P. Angelova-Gateva, 'Za efekta na hipodinamiata varhu nyakoi funktsii i obmenni protsesi na mladia i stareeshtia organizam', *PGG*, 5 (1969), 97–104.

⁶⁶ P. Angelova et al., 'Otnosno funktsionalnoto natovarvane s fizicheski uprazhnenia s nasochenost kam izdrazhlivost kato sredstvo za aktivna profilaktika pri hora v sredna I naprednala vazrast', *PGG*, 3 (1967), 209–21; L. Valnarov and P. Dobrev, 'Niakoi promeni v elektrokardiografskia obraz u vazrastni, funktsionalno natovarvani sas silovi uprazhnenia', *PGG*, 5 (1969), 105–15.

⁶⁷ P. Angelova, 'Varhu niakoi osobenosti na vaglehidratnata obmiana v muskuli pri hipodinamia', *PGG*, 3 (1967), 156–61; D. Mateev, P. Angelova, E. Tsvetanova, 'Izsledvane na opredelena enzimna konstelatsia pri fizicheska aktivnost na hora ot 57- do 77-godishma vyzrast', *PGG*, 4 (1969), 219–24; D. Mateev, L. Shikova, Iv. Minchev, G. Chavrakov, St. Gagov, 'Niakoi morfologichni problemi pri obezdvizheni zaitsi', *PGG*, 5 (1969), 57–63.

⁶⁸ I. Petrov, 'Promeni v niakoi subektivni pokazateli, imashti otnoshenie kam vegetativnata ravnovesnost u vyzrastni i stari hora pod vazdeistvieto na funktsionalno natovarvane s fizicheski uprazhnenia', *PGG*, 2 (1966), 143–53; I. Petrov, 'Trigodishno longitudinalno proslediyavane na pametta posredstvom modifitsiran test na Jacobson u vyzrastni i stari hora, zhiveeshti v dom za socialni grizhi, sas i bez funktsionalno natovarvane s fizicheski uprazhnenia i kulturterapia', *PGG*, 5 (1969), 83–95; I. Petrov, K. Konstantinov, 'Psihichni promeni pod vazdeistvie na funktsionalno natovarvane u vyzrastni hora', *PGG*, 6 (1971), 221–30.

ageing with healthy individuals and their therapeutic effect in cases of chronic diseases.⁶⁹ The Social Gerontology department studied aspects of post-retirement life, including attitudes to work and willingness to continue work after retirement.⁷⁰ In this context, the idea of active ageing was articulated in a categorisation of the elderly according to their physical and intellectual capacities: from 'inactive' (who needed comprehensive care), through 'individually active' (who could cope with their daily life) and 'socially active' (who could provide care within their family) to 'economically active' (who had retained their capacity to work outside the home). Consequently, the aim was to develop 're-activation' programmes tailored for each group.⁷¹ Hence, the assessment of the work capacity of elderly people was seen as an important task of social gerontology.⁷²

In this way, Mateev's theory was comprehensively tested and developed, primarily on volunteers among the residents of the Home for the Elderly No 11 on the outskirts of Sofia, in the course of several years during which dozens of anthropometric, physiometric, haemodynamic and biochemical indicators were monitored.⁷³ About half of the articles published in the CGG yearbook *Problemi na gerontologijata i geriatrijata* scrutinized aspects of Mateev's theory based on extensive experiments.

The ideas of the beneficial effects of physical activities found their way to broad audiences as well: in 1966, Mateev initiated a popular book with the attractive title 'Can everyone be long-lived'. In the first chapter, he introduced his theory in an easily understandable manner based on dense data from experiments proving it. The following chapters were penned by his collaborators: Georgi Stoynev on the demography and social aspects of ageing and longevity in Bulgaria, Ignat Petrov on the psychological and intellectual changes in old age, and Enyu Boyadjiev on recommended physical activities and exercises. Evidently, the questions addressed in the book were intriguing for the readers and its content implied a positive answer to the question in the title, showing the road to longevity: in the following 10 years it underwent two more editions with print-runs exceeding 10 thousand, a proof of success at the Bulgarian book market.⁷⁴

Under Mateev's leadership, the CGG formed very much of a paradigm in T. Kuhn's sense: a research community sharing and jointly applying a common approach, common

⁶⁹ G. Stoynev, E. Boyadjiev, T. Krasteva, 'Promeni v niakoi antropometrichni pokazateli pod vlianie na fizicheski uprazhnenia u stari hora sas zaboliavania na oporno-dvigatelna aparat', *PGG*, 2 (1966), 87–91; G. Karaneshev, 'Niakoi nabliudenia pri zanimavashti se s fizikultura vyzrastni hora s povisheno kravno naliagane', *PGG*, 5 (1969), 127–29; N. Vladimirova et al., 'Promeni vav funktsionalnite pokazateli u vyzrastni hora pod vlianie na lechebna fizikultura', *PGG*, 6 (1971), 256–8.

⁷⁰ Ts. Doychinova, 'Po vaprosa za socialnoto obezpechavane na vyzrastnite i starite hora', *PGG*, 4 (1969), 173–92; L. Vlahliiska, 'Problemat za svobodnoto vreme v starostta i niakoi vidove aktivnosti za vyzrastni i stari hora', *PGG*, 4 (1969), 205–17; G. Stoynev, Ts. Doychinova, St. Vizev, 'Prouchvane varhu ikonomicheskata aktivnost na litsa v pensionna vyzrast', *PGG*, 6 (1971), 36–41.

⁷¹ L. Valnarov, 'Predmet, istoria i zadachi na gerontologijata', *PGG*, 1 (1965), 33–43.

⁷² G. Stoynev, 'Medico-sotsialni problemi v gerontologijata i geriatrijata', *PGG*, 1 (1965), 90–107, 104.

⁷³ D. Mateev et al., 'Promeni v antropometrichnite, fiziometrichnite, hemodinamichnite i biokhimichnite pokazateli u vyzrastni i stari hora pod vlianie na ednogodishno funktsionalno natovarvane s fizicheski uprazhnenia', *PGG*, 2 (1966), 93–141; Mateev et al., 'Trigodishni longitudinalni izsledvania varhu hora v naprednala i starcheska vyzrast sas i bez funktsionalno natovarvane s fizicheski uprazhnenia i kulturterapia', *PGG*, 4 (1969), 13–96.

⁷⁴ D. Mateev, G. Stoynev, I. Petrov, E. Boyadjiev, *Mozhe li vseki da bade dalgoletnik* (3rd ed., Sofia 1977).

concepts, assumptions, models and explanatory frames. It developed a rather comprehensive trans-disciplinary understanding of ageing and old age, and a corresponding model of gerontology as an integral science, a field of knowledge drawing on biological, medical and human sciences, and bordering with clinical practice on the one hand, and social care, on the other. The CGG team saw the tasks of gerontology within this paradigm: to understand the biological causes and the physiological characteristics of ageing, as well as the causes for premature ageing, and to develop methods of prophylactics and therapy for it. The ultimate goal of gerontology was formulated in the rhetoric of the time as ‘struggle for longevity and healthy ageing’ through the development of ‘dedicated methods for life extension’.⁷⁵

Only a few months after Mateev’s death however, the CGG was merged into the Department of Endocrinology to form in 1972 the Research Institute of Endocrinology, Gerontology and Geriatrics (RIEGG) within the newly re-organized Medical Academy. The merger led to certain changes in its paradigm – i.e. the very conception of gerontology and its research programme – in the direction of its narrower medicalization. The question was no longer about distinguishing between natural and premature ageing but about the pathologies of ageing and old age. In line with the research priorities set by the Ministry of Public Health, the Gerontology division focused in the 1970s and 1980s mainly on atherosclerosis. Laboratory research included the study of lipid metabolism at the level of organisms (experimental animals), tissues and cells. Epidemiological research had to establish the spread of atherosclerosis among the population aged over 45, while applied research experimented with a special diet administered to the residents of a care home for old people. Indeed, this was not the only focus of gerontology during that period.⁷⁶ On-going projects were not discontinued, but the new ones had to be tailored to fit with the research of the endocrinology division, which had the leading role in the RIEGG. With the merger, the CGG yearbook was discontinued and the researchers from the gerontology division published in different medical journals depending on their specialization, for example *Nevrologia*, *Psihiatria i Nevrohirurgia*, *Bulgarski Oftalmologichen Pregled*, and abroad. While most of these outlets were rather prestigious, the lack of a periodical specialized in gerontology led to the gradual dispersal of gerontological research into other branches of medicine. Furthermore, research based on laboratory methods and relying on specialized disciplines such as biochemistry and pathophysiology enjoyed greater professional power and prestige in comparison with other fields, such as psychology, psychiatry and physical therapy.⁷⁷

What were the consequences of these developments for the science-based imagining of old age and old people? While research on atherosclerosis was no doubt important for understanding the pathologies of ageing, its decisive privileging at RIEGG, as well as the focus on pathology, combined with a systematic under-resourcing of other research themes, tended to import a certain unidimensionality into the paradigm of gerontology developed there, as against the more multidisciplinary and integrated CGG model. The interest was no

⁷⁵ L. Valnarov, ‘Predmet, istoria i zadachi na gerontologijata’, *PGG*, 1 (1965), 33–43, 41.

⁷⁶ Report on the fulfillment of the research plan for 1972. State Archive, Sofia, holding 2265 (RIEGG), inv. 1, a. u. 9, sheets 4, 8–13.

⁷⁷ Such a situation was not unique for Bulgaria. Cf. Katz, *Disciplining Old Age*, 113.

longer in the positive examples of longevity but in the cases of pathological ageing and their treatment. Hence the subject of research turned out to be no longer old people, some of whom were sick, but rather sick people, some of whom were old. The focus on pathological ageing reduced old people to patients rather than active individuals capable of making their own choices. The ‘medical gaze’ (Foucault) framing this paradigm tended towards a ‘naturalist model’ aiming ‘to see, to isolate features, to recognize those that are identical and those that are different, to regroup them, to classify them’, bracketing out everything else.⁷⁸ This in turn led to a certain objectification of the old people: they came to be regarded primarily as clients of medical institutions, as objects of examination and care, and the knowledge production about old age became primarily the terrain of medicine. The medical gaze formed the structures of perception and thinking not only about the nature of illness but also – and in the same direction – about the nature of ageing. The focus on pathologies made ageing appear as pathology in itself and old people – as sick people in need for care and treatment.

4. Conclusions

I tried to demonstrate three hegemonic ways of constructing old age and shaping the social imaginaries of it in communist Bulgaria: through the authoritative discourse of ideology, through the policies toward retired people, and through science/gerontology. They all contributed to a historically structured life course, based on political, bureaucratic and medical standardisation. These discourses largely developed in parallel, without much referring to each other. Ageing and old people ‘looked’ differently depending on the lens through which they were viewed and the social and political context in which this lens was applied. Yet, at some points they also echoed and amplified each other.

The ideological discourse underwent a curious evolution from seeing old people as ‘senile reaction’ to representing them as custodians of national traditions, thereby changing sides in the relations between societal generations. The very notion of old age was developed in the context of intergenerational relations, often metaphorically sliding between societal/political generations and generations in the family. Thus ‘old fathers’ were initially pictured as bearers of the values of the previous regime, while ‘old communists’ and ‘old masters’ were cast in a positive light. During the later years of the regime, while promoting ‘economically active’ pensioners, the party newspaper increasingly emphasized the young’s duty to take care of the elders in their families. Occasional campaigns of naming and shaming were waged against ‘ungrateful’ sons and daughters who did not take proper care of their old parents. Thus the ‘problem’ of ageing and the aged was not seen as a structural one, requiring targeted state policies, but rather as a moral one. The view that care for the elders was a moral duty of their children was reflected in the Family Code of 1985.

While granting some state care to lonely old people through nursing homes, the policies toward the elderly, as articulated in the pension legislature from 1960s on were mostly concerned with economic productivity. Hence retirees were viewed primarily as a labour resource to be tapped into. The conditions for their return to work formed a persistent

⁷⁸ M. Foucault, *The Birth of the Clinic: An Archaeology of Medical Perception* (London 1976), 89.

theme and a matter of numerous regulations. Pensioners' labour was very much desired in the situation of labour shortage, especially in some branches of the economy and on unqualified, unattractive positions, sometimes in harmful working environments. The authoritative discourse in *Rabotnichesko Delo* contributed by featuring 'economically active' retirees continuing to work precisely in those unattractive sectors. However, there is no evidence that any of the gerontologists' recommendations of 'gerohygienic measures' such as medical checks, reducing the scope and intensity of work, creating a suitable work environment, etc., were taken into account.⁷⁹ While the law appeared as gender-neutral, most of the branches where pensioners' labour was sought, such as mining, construction and forestry, needed male workers. Female retirees, at the same time, were pushed into their traditional roles of caregivers and homemakers.

Finally, in the early period of its existence, gerontology developed within a relatively holistic paradigm focusing on the importance of active ageing, including physical, social and intellectual activities. This focus, though not explicitly prioritizing 'residual work capacity', was to a significant extent in line with the conception of the pensioners as labour reserve. Later on, gerontology tended to see older people primarily through the lens of biomedical research and clinical practice, focusing on bodies, their organs, tissues and metabolisms. With the focus mainly on the pathologies of ageing, the construction of old age turned out to be largely a therapeutic one, searching for symptoms of disease. Thus policy and science developed disparate images of ageing: while post-retirement labour was increasingly promoted at policy level, gerontology leaned towards medicalization of ageing and old age, representing old people as objects of care. This was however specialized therapeutic care, rather than the intergenerational care as moral duty, called for in the party newspaper. The discourse of dependency advocated by this gerontological paradigm and partly by the official daily, ran counter to the reliance on the elderly as labour reserve both for the labour market and for unpaid work in the family.

In spite of the divergences and the asynchronies, there were common features of the three discourses, namely, a homogenising perspective towards the elderly. They appeared as a single entity with almost no differentiation according to gender, age, physical and mental condition, place of residence, family status. Applying simplistic, often stereotypical assumptions to 'the aged' as a category, they – especially the ideology and the policy – tended to gloss over diversity and complexities. What was generally missing was the interest, the voice and the perspective of the elderly. It appears as if old age, with its various characteristics, was imposed on the elderly people 'from outside', without their participation and often depriving them of agency.

STATEMENTS AND DECLARATIONS

Ethical considerations: Not applicable.

Consent to participate: Not applicable.

Consent to publication: Not applicable.

⁷⁹ Stoynev, Doychinova, Vizev, Prouchvane, 41. Unlike the Institute of Gerontology in Kiev (Kiyv), where gerohygiene constituted a separate department dealing with work and living conditions, nutrition, leisure and physical activities, demography and geography of ageing (D. F. Chebotaryov, *Vospominania* [Kiyv 2008], 184-5), in Bulgaria this concept had a limited use and a narrower meaning referring to work environments and their suitability/adaptation for elderly workers.

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